

INVESTIGATING THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS IN SCHOOLS OF KURDISTAN PROVINCE, IRAN

Loghman Karami^{1*}, Elahe Danesh Rad²

¹MA., Sport Management, Sanandaj Branch, Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj, Iran

²MA., Sport Management, Karaj Branch, Islamic Azad University, Karaj, Iran

Abstract:

The present study has done with the purpose of investigating factors influencing the development of sports in schools of Kurdistan province. In terms of goal, this study is functional; in terms of strategy is survey –descriptive that was conducted as field. The statistical population includes all sport teachers (894 individuals) and professors of physical education of Universities of Kurdistan province (26 individuals) (N=920) that were active during 2015-2016 academic year in that province. The sample size was calculated 275 using Morgan table and sampling was done by targeting and available method for academic professors and for sport teachers cluster and simple random sampling was done. In order to study the objectives of this study the researcher made questionnaires was constructed which contains 28 item questionnaires that by using similar researches and literature of research prepared in the Likert 5 item. 9 experts in the field of physical education tried to confirm face validity and the content of the questionnaire and the reliability of the questionnaire obtained $\alpha=0.81$ by the pilot implementation on the 40 members of the research community and by calculating Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The binomial test was used for data analysis. It should be noted that in this study SPSS version 22 was used for data analyzing. Results showed that economic, social and cultural, organizational management, facilities and sports equipment, technology and political factors influencing the development of school sports in the Kurdistan province. It became clear that prioritize of components and items affecting development of sports schools in the Kurdistan province Are different that according to these findings, recommends to Department of Education in Kurdistan

ⁱ Correspondence: email loghmankarami@yahoo.com

province that provide necessary measurements to promote the development of sports schools.

Keywords: influencing factors, developing sport school, Kurdistan province

Introduction

More than 2000 years ago, Hippocrates, the Greek physician about the needs of human to continuous activities, stated that physical activity is essential for health and the limbs of human body in case of having moderate and continuous physical exercises, they would maintain their health and became powerful, their lifetime increase and provided that loco motor activity stay away from their daily lives, their body limbs becomes lazy and becomes ready to accept a variety of diseases, and their growth rate reduced and the speed of life increased and aging in humans is expedited (Zang et al, 2011). However, physical education and sport have not been separated from ancient times as an independent entity, yet they used it with the activities of other entities, in order to train the body, powerful, the intellectual and moral development of the individuals in accordance with its ideology and used it more to combat readiness. Along with the progress of human thought, many scholars in the field of education and its effects on the development of human excellence had tried to conduct research and constructing theories. Since physical education constituted an important part of education, it gradually emerged as an independent and it gradually emerged as an independent and separate entity science entity. This has been due to the indispensable effects that has had especially in childhood, adolescence and youth times (Khalaji, 2015). With the progress of the science through time and becoming more civilized of the human and living in the cities and the invention of the first steam engine in 1777 (Ghafoori et al, 2004), then using diverse machines as a complement or substitute for human resources, gradually, the pressure that was entered to the body from the daily life, decreased so that currently, the human muscle activities substituted by electronic and machine devices.

According to the changes that have occurred in the way of human life and the dynamic life that has established in his existence for million years and hereditary was transmitted from generation to generation, within two hundred years became stagnation thus human could not able to coordinate him with poverty motor in terms of habits, mood, emotions, instinct and genetics and maintain his health and physical and mental balance (Azizi, 2008). Doing sport activities is a solution to get rid of poverty motor that is caused by machine life. At the present time, exercise is one of the ways

that people can use it to overcome stress. People who exercise regularly are less likely than others suffering from heart attacks. Their brain takes more rest; their heart beat decreases during rest, feel less pressure and have more confidence, they are more optimistic and less depressed. Thus considering the importance of attending people in sporting activities, and taking advantage of the beneficial effects of exercise as the positive effects of physical, emotional, mental, social and economic has caused governments to think about planning and investing in the sports and healthy recreations (Momtaz Bakhsh and Fakor, 2008). The development of sport in the community can have several beneficial effects which among them we can refer to increase in the level of public health, improving social relations of human societies, improving the productivity and the workability of human resources, enrichment leisure time (Kaliopi et al, 2008). In this regard, it should be noted that the positive effects of early childhood in children can be created and schools are the most important social bases to do it which in this research they can be addressed.

Sport is a social phenomenon that enjoys a high priority as a cultural and human need. Physical education and sport in general and championship sport in particular is more important for students as half of society because the development of our society depends on the strength and abilities of all its members (Edington, Edgerton, 2012). Physical education is a training process that aims to improve performance and human performance and development through physical activity. Physical education includes acquisition motor skills; maintain physical fitness in order to general health, attain knowledge and develop good impression of physical activity (Khalaji, 2015). The researchers believe that not only in childhood, youth and university but also throughout the life of people in this profession this mission should be accomplished (Estela et al, 2014). Thus physical education teachers and authorities must be at the service of students in all age groups with different characteristics. Physical education enjoys special status in the school curriculum to achieve the objectives of the education system. It can be used as a most important tool to achieve to the objectives of training, and public education due to its special structure and also due to the natural and inherent tendency of being consistent with the needs of students (Chakra Bourti et al, 2012). Today sport is seen as different aspects such as training sport, public sport and recreation, championship and professional sports.

Development of physical education and sport as a healthy underlying supply and training of human resources is considered part of national development plans (Comprehensive system of physical education and sport, 2004). Exercise is important at all times but human life but since the basis of physical and mental training is laid in childhood and adolescence must give more importance to sports in this period. Sport in

addition to cause students to have good entertainment to spend leisure time has many effects on their physical and psychological health. Many of the adverse effects of social environment, economic, familial status, inheritance and so on using exercise can be reduced or even completely eliminating (Bagherzadeh et al, 2003). Therefore, physical training educations have significant impact on students' training and if it's practical application to be performed in principle will have great influence on the development of physical, mental, social, psychological, morale and ethics in students (Kargar Fard and Nderian, 2012). Education, treatment, and promotion of literacy and education of people in every society are among the important factors in the development of each country in different cultural, social, economic, political, etc. Education also plays a role in the growth and prosperity of any society and especially students and if their programs are properly formulated and execute provides opportunities for young people of society in addition to improve one, be prepare as an active and efficient forces. Physical education and sports are an integral part of education, especially in adolescence and young, not only as an input in the education system is considered by most experts in education and physical education but as one of the most important factors in improving the quality and quantity of the output of the operational processes of each educational institution and why is that developed and developing countries are trying to develop serious investing to perform education and physical education goals in the process and trying to continuously promote the level of functioning and its achievements(Mozaffari et al, 2010).

Shabani Bahar et al (2009) in a research concluded that the factors of educational objectives, curriculum, educational content, teaching methods, professional sports teachers, experienced teachers, exercise, attitude and evaluation high or very high effective on the quality of physical education. Also Roy (2010) concluded that physical education leads to development and improving physical, psychological, social and culture status and although life at the present time provides entertainment and enough experiences for people but also physical education should be part of school educational programs. Physical education programs in schools have clear goals. Physical education teachers and planners must have been familiar with the objectives of this lesson and justify them citing the reasons, evidence and scientific resources for students and their parents, If the objectives of physical education programs at every level of education (elementary, middle, secondary) be expressed clearly, In this case, all persons involved in the preparation or implementation of programs will be able to attain the response to this important question that "*Why and for what purpose they try*" (Ramazani Nejad, 2014). In this regard it should be noted that many factors, such as family, social, economic and economic participation in sports can be effective in sports activities especially education

and training. Also in different contexts, they have stated incentives such as the need for physical activity, immunizations against diseases, weight loss, learn a variety of sports... as motivation for participation in physical activity and sport (Comprehensive system of physical education and sport, 2004). Nowadays, physical education has become considered as an undeniable necessity and an essential foundation for all communities. The positive effects of this phenomenon are providing the health and physical and mental health reducing health care costs, increasing production and productivity of all citizens, etc. The issue of physical education as a means of recreation and leisure can be an effective tool for the prevention of social deviations especially drug addiction. The fact is fully accepted that sports activities for the general public are useful and valuable. In other words, all people in every age group must do activities to have a healthy body and spirit (Khalaji, 2015).

A large part of our society (35.16 percent) of the population includes students (Statistical Yearbook of the country, 2015) that make up almost age range of 6 to 21 years (Higher Education Council, 2001) and if the majority of the population can be properly managed in the way of sports and physical activity, we can hoped to improve the lives of their future. Participating students in sports activities inside and outside the educational environment, is useful in the process of education and the academic achievement and on the other hand can lead to progress to other levels of exercise and an active lifestyle. Therefore it is essential that numerous studies done in this area and the factors and obstacles facing this level of exercise be examined; unfortunately, in the field of sports schools in the province of Kurdistan have not been any research conducted It seems essential that the research done in this area. Hence, the researcher decided that by studying effective factors on the school sports of Kurdistan province, in this regard, taken important and effective step to develop sports schools and make great help to development of the school sport. Today, the time spent on physical activities of adolescents in the last three decades largely reduced (Bidel and Godas, 1996). However, about one-sixth of the country's populations are students (Statistical Yearbook of the country, 2015). Considering that a large population of our country to various causes suffering from poverty motor and this could have negative and damaging consequences, requires that in this regard, the solution for this problem be found (Safarzadeh, 1997). In this regard, the Kurdistan province is also not excluded by the barriers and faced with challenges that could endanger the health of whole strata of the population in the province. Therefore, the researcher is faced with the question: What are the factors affecting school sports of Kurdistan.

Methods

This study aimed to investigate the factors influencing the development of sports in schools of Kurdistan province. In terms of goal, this study is functional; in terms of strategy is survey –descriptive that was conducted as field. The statistical population includes all sport teachers (894 individuals) and professors of physical education of Universities of Kurdistan province (26 individuals) (N=920) that were active during 2015-2016 academic year in that province. The sample size was calculated 275 using Morgan table and sampling was done by targeting and available method for academic professors and for sport teachers cluster and simple random sampling was done. In order to study the objectives of this study the researcher made questionnaires was constructed which contains 28 item questionnaires that by using similar researches and literature of research prepared in the Likert 5 item. 9 experts in the field of physical education tried to confirm face validity and the content of the questionnaire and the reliability of the questionnaire obtained $\alpha = 0.81$ by the pilot implementation on the 40 members of the research community and by calculating Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The binomial test was used for data analysis. It should be noted that in this study SPSS version 22 was used for data analyzing.

Findings

According to findings of the study since none of loadings factors has not placed in the range of -96.1 to +96.1 thus the agent loads are significant and involved in explaining the variables. According to obtained results it was cleared that from 275 participants 112 person were women and 163 were men, also results showed that from 275 participants 30 person had diploma and under diploma degree, 44 person had associated degree, 75 person had bachelor degree, 91 persons had MA degree and 35 person had PhD degree that the most frequency related to MA degree.

a. Economic factors effective the development of the province's sports schools.

Table 1: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of economic factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Economic	Group 1	≤ 3	228	0.83	%50	0.001
	Group 2	> 3	47	0.17		
	Total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of economic factor significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that economic factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

b. Social factors effective the development of the province's sports schools.

Table 2: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of social factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Cultural-social	Group 1	≤ 3	228	0.80	%50	0.001
	Group 2	> 3	54	0.2		
	Total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of social-cultural factor significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that social-cultural factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

c. Organizational and managerial factors are influencing the development of the province's sports schools.

Table 3: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of organizational and managerial factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Organizational and managerial factor	Group 1	≤ 3	217	0.79	%50	0.001
	Group 2	> 3	58	0.21		
	Total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of organizational and managerial factor significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that organizational and managerial factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

d. Facilities and equipment are influencing factors in the development of school sports Kurdistan province.

Table 4: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of Facilities and Equipment factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Facilities and Equipment factor	Group 1	≤ 3	208	0.76	%50	0.001
	Group 2	> 3	67	0.24		
	Total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of Facilities and Equipment factor significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that Facilities and Equipment factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

e. Technology is influencing factor in the development of school sports Kurdistan province.

Table 5: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of technology factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Facilities and Equipment factor	Group 1	≤ 3	204	0.74	%50	0.001
	Group 2	> 3	71	0.26		
	Total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of technology factor significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that technology factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

f. Political factor influencing the development of the province's sports schools

Table 6: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of Political factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Political factor	Group 1	≤ 3	200	0.73	%50	0.001
	Group2	> 3	75	0.27		
	total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of political factor significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that political factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

g. Training and technical factors influencing the development of the province's sports schools

Table 7: Estimate binomial test to study mean difference of Training and technical factor with assumed mean

Element	Groups	Classes	Number	The observed ratio with %	Ratio of the test	Two-way significance level
Training and technical factors	Group 1	≤ 3	197	0.72	%50	0.001
	Group2	> 3	78	0.28		
	total		275	1.00		

The values of above table indicates that the mean of Training and technical factors significantly higher than assumed mean ($\text{sig} \leq 0.05$). So we can say that political factor is effective in the development of the province's sports schools.

The affecting factors on the development of sports schools of Kurdistan province have different priorities.

Table 8: Friedman test results

Number	275
Chi square	28.555
Degrees of freedom	6
The significance level	0.001

Table 9: Prioritize the influencing factors in development school sports

Aspects	The mean of rank	Rank
Technology	4.22	First
Sport equipment's and facilities	4.18	Second
Political	4.12	Third
Organizational and managerial	4.06	Fourth
Technical and educational	4.02	Fifth
Cultural-social	4.00	Sixth
Economical	3.39	Seventh

According to the results of the table, given that the significance of Friedman ANOVA test, is smaller than error level, as a result with 95 percent confidence we can say that there is meaningful difference between 7 effective components on the sport development of schools of Kurdistan province .as can be see the technology aspect with mean of 4.22 has the first rank and has the best rank and economical aspect with 3.39 mean with seventh rank has the low rank. Then, we can say that the assumption that

the factors influencing factors in development sports schools of Kurdistan province have different priorities.

In the figure 1, results of research model was showed:

Figure 1: Results of research model

Discussion and Conclusion

Today's mechanical life and passive life-style of people, causing many problems and diseases associated with poor movement and sports activities is a solution to get rid of motor poverty and consequently deceases and problems occurring from it. Exercise is one of the ways that people can use it to overcome on stress and physical illnesses such as cardiovascular disease. The researchers believe that not only in childhood, youth, university, but also throughout the life of people in this profession should do this mission to be accomplished (Stella et al, 2014).it means that physical education teachers and officials should make possibilities to students to do it. Physical education lesson has special place in the school curriculum to achieve the objectives of the education system.

This lesson can be used as an effective tool to reach the goals of educating,

training because it has practical and special nature and it is align with natural needs and desires of students (Chakraborti et al, 2012). Therefore, physical education significant impact on students in schools to foster and if it's practical application in principle to be performed would have great influence on the development of physical, mental, social, psychological, morale and ethics in students. Today, the time spent on physical activities of adolescents in the last three decades has decreased significantly. However, about one-sixth of the country's population is students. Considering that the great amount of the population of our country due to different reasons suffering from poverty motor and this can have negative and destructive consequences, requires that doing something about this issue. This will be achieved once the enough funding through the Department of Education is dedicated to sports schools.

The organizational and managerial obstacles, effective on the sport development can be cases such as poor monitoring in dealing with sport in Kurdistan school, way of implementation, coordination between the concerned agencies and monitoring and infrastructure problems of sports in schools, hence, if correctly identify problems and obstacles to the process and procedures properly managed. It seems that provide the context the developing of sport in the schools of Kurdistan province. In relation to the problems of lack of resources and lack of funding has also affected the work of administrative officials and managers. Non-specialist managers and officials is another effective reason. Senior administration officials and even representatives can pass a law that in department of physical training of Education & Training department is one of the most sensitive parts do activities about employment specialist persons. It is no secret that at the present time, to succeed in any particular technology, it should use the particular technology. In particular, the agencies and departments need to updated technologies to achieve the goals and vision of the organization. Ministry of Education and consequently all provincial education departments should have foresights to develop and promote sports in schools, and to achieve its vision, have long-term planning in all fields, particularly new and up to date technologies. Lack of resources and technology has been the reluctance of teachers and it would be very damaging consequences for society because schools are the center of education. And this important mission is the responsibility of working teachers and unmotivated teachers have a direct impact on children's education. Meet new technologies could also be the reason for the weakness of society. Organizations can use the empower people held the classes to refresh his staff. There is no doubt that the technology in the sport leads to progress. More importantly, existence technology in schools can even ensure the sport future of our country. Because with discovery the genuine talent that exists in our country and fostering them, we can guarantee the future of our country. These findings

are consistent with findings of Askarzadeh and Heydarnejad (2012), Palomäki & Heikinaro-Johansson (2013), Gur et al (2011), Stran & Curtner-Smith (2010) Maki and Sjostrend (2007), Shafter (2005) and Aldosari (2004).

References

1. Azizi, Bisotoon. (2008). investigate the attitudes of the students living in dormitories of Tehran University, Master's Thesis of Sports Management. University of Tehran
2. Bagher Zadeh, F.; hemeyattalab, R., Mottaghipour, M. (2010). Investigate the causes of female high school students in extracurricular activities, *Move*, Issue 11, pp. 23-31.
3. Edington, D. W., Adgrtvn him. Reggie. (2011). *Biology of Physical Activity* (Translation by Hojjat Allah Nikbakht). Tehran: Samt Publication, the first edition, Eighth Edition.
4. Ghafori Farhad, Rahman Seresht, H, Kozechian, H, Ehsani, M. (2004). Study of Physical Education professional's attitude toward the role of mass media (Radio, television and publications) in the case of interest in athletics and universal sports. *The Journal of Harekat*, Issue 16, pp. 57-78.
5. Kalliopi, S., Shilbury D., Christine, G. (2008). Sport Development Systems, Policies and Pathways: An Introduction to the Special Issue. *Sport Management Review*, Vol. 11, pp. 217-223.
6. Khalaji, H. (2014). *Principles of Physical Education*. Tehran: Payame noor University.
7. Momtaz Bakhsh, Maryam, Fakor .U. (2008). Investigating the mechanisms used to promote and develop sport for women in Military Sciences University. *Quarterly disciplinary knowledge*, the ninth year, the second edition, pp. 53-61
8. Mozaffari, Seyed Amir Ahmad, a certain person, MR, pour Sultan, Hussein, overlooking Javadi, B., Ismail, and Mohammad Reza. (2010). Describe the implementation status of physical education and sport in first grade of primary school teachers and administrators in the of the country, *Movement and exercise Journal*, Vol. VII, Issue 14, Pages 119-139
9. Ramezaninejad, Rahim. (2013). *Physical education in schools*. Tehran, the publisher, Eighth Edition
10. Safarzade Reza. (1997). studies secondary school student's city neighborhoods leisure activities with an emphasis on physical activity. Thesis of Master Physical Education. Islamic Azad University Central Tehran Branch.

11. Shabani Bahar, GR, mystical, Nasrallah, Ashraghi, Amir. (2009). Investigate the influential factors the quality to physical education teachers in secondary schools from the perspective of sports. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, No. 20, pp. 143-156.
12. Stella K. Muthuri., Lucy-Joy M. Wachira., Allana G. Leblanc., Claire E. Francis., Margaret Sampson., Vincent O. Onywera and Mark S. Tremblay. (2014). Temporal Trends and Correlates of Physical Activity, Sedentary Behavior, and Physical Fitness among School-Aged Children in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2014, 11(3), 3327-3359.
13. Zeng, Howard Z.; Hipscher, Michael; Leung, Reymond W. (2011). Attitudes of High School Students toward Physical Education and Their Sport Activity Preferences. *Journal of Social Sciences* 7 (4): 529-537.

Loghman Karami, Elahe Danesh Rad
INVESTIGATING THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS
IN SCHOOLS OF KURDISTAN PROVINCE, IRAN

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).